

D7.7: Agricultural Insurance Enablers - Advisory Board report (4)

WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion

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BEACON

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List of Acronyms

Acronyms	Explanation
AB	Advisory Board
AgI	Agricultural Insurance
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
UA	Underwriting Agency
WP	Work Package
LHC	Lighthouse Customers

Executive summary

The current Deliverable 7.7: "Agricultural Insurance Enablers (4)" Advisory Board (AB) report, provides an overview of the main discussion points and feedback received during this 4th reporting period. It presents the AgI Enablers recommendations over the Project progress and specifically their suggestions on the EO index insurance module, Blockchain component, Smart Contract Function and Business Models, as well as their final evaluation of the BEACON tool. Additionally, a collection of all AB recommendations and their implementation in the BEACON process are presented.

The document is structured in 5 chapters. The first Chapter presents an overview of the AgI Enablers and their role within the project. The second Chapter includes an overview of the previous three versions of this Deliverable. The feedback received by the AgI Enablers over this reporting period is presented in the third Chapter. The next chapter concludes the AgI Enablers recommendations and presents how they were fully elaborated within the project, whilst the last Chapter of this deliverable presents the final conclusions.

All the activity related to the BEACON AgI Enablers – Advisory Board within the project duration, falls under the implementation of WP7 – Dissemination, Communication and Diffusion, led by the project partner ETAM SA, and relative Deliverables (D7.4-7.7). The current deliverable D7.7 AgI Enablers – Advisory Board report (4) is the final of the four relevant deliverables that were developed within the project timeline.

2. Overview of past AgI Enablers reports

The first deliverable (D 7.4) described the role of the AB and their selection process. Over the first reporting period, four out of the six AgI Enablers were selected. The AgI enablers were invited to an introductory meeting where they were provided with an overview of the BEACON project, they were introduced to their role as members of the AgI Enablers group and a dynamic interaction on the challenges of the project was initiated. These meetings resulted in their first recommendations that led to specific actions within BEACON workplan.

Over the second reporting period (D 7.5) two additional members were added to the AgI Enablers group and introductory meetings were carried out as in the first iteration of AB members. Additional experts' recommendations for the project's implementation were received and relative mitigation actions were taken.

The third deliverable (D 7.6) tackled the disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in the production and marketing of agricultural goods all around the world. With the pandemic bringing an additional focus on agriculture and allied activities, the need to consider how insurance coverage can support the sector was investigated and the opportunities the project presented to mitigate its effect on the sector was investigated with feedback received by the AgI enablers.

3. Interviews overview

3.1 Planning and deviations

Over this period three AgI Enablers meetings had been planned. Nonetheless due to prior engagements of the AgI Enablers group only one meeting was realized. According to the risk management plan of the project additional feedback was received via a structured questionnaire.

3.2 The BEACON AgI Enablers meeting

The BEACON AgI Enablers meeting was held online, and the goal was to update the members of the AB on the progress of the project, initiate a discussion on project results and receive their recommendations. The agenda of the meeting held on the 28th of June was the following:

- 🌐 Project progress: Gregory Mygdakos, KARAVIAS, Project Coordinator
- 🌐 EO index insurance module: Christoph Mussenbrock, ETHERISC
- 🌐 Blockchain component and Smart Contract Function, Agathoklis Dimitrakos, AgroApps
- 🌐 Discussion and recommendations

The meeting on behalf of the AgI Enablers group was attended by Ms Eleni Vakaki, an Earth Observation expert - index insurance specialist, and Ms Shilpa Pankaj, the Vice president with Guy Carpenter's Asia Pacific team. The meeting was organized by ETAM SA and the Consortium was represented by members of all Consortium partners.

The main recommendations of the AgI group members are presented in the following:

Use data for related risks for pricing as an additional service

Eleni Vakaki: Data for related risks are being used for damage assessment within the BEACON toolbox. These data can potentially be utilized from the pricing point of view, which is also important as all those risks could be underwritten. Pricing information could thus additionally be provided for these risks.

BEACON: Expand current underwriting service by complimenting weather - yield and third source data with past claims and losses data. Considering that such data are already captured by AgI companies it could be a further expansion of BEACON.

Communicate and monitor pest and disease risk alerts

Eleni Vakaki: Pest and diseases risk alerts should be communicated both to insurance companies and farmers. Farmers should also be monitored for their actions to mitigate risks.

BEACON: One of the main BEACON services is the forecasting of pests and diseases. The insurance companies were able to monitor and receive early warnings with regards to the possibility of the occurrence of pests and diseases. Therefore, the insurance companies were able to communicate these alerts to their clients through the mobile application or, if they wanted/needed, through direct communication, in order for the farmers to receive the proper actions. In addition, based on the companies' and their clients' needs, the mobile application was populated with relevant services and farmers had direct access to such alerts.

Translate alerts into actionable agricultural advice

Eleni Vakaki: In case the AgI companies decide to circulate the information, it would be useful to translate alerts into actionable agricultural advice.

BEACON: Indeed, this information is of great importance. Through the mobile application, the farmers had access to crop monitoring through relevant vegetation indices. On the other hand, based on the alerts received, especially, regarding imminent extreme weather events, the insurance companies were able to communicate to their clients, either through the BEACON solutions or directly, measures and advices that could be essential for their agricultural practices.

Pricing and underwriting of climate change

Shilpa Pankaj: The BEACON model should be factoring in the impact of climate change on pricing and underwriting.

BEACON: The climatology module is fed with historical data that date back to 50+ years for any type of field or indices. Additionally, weather forecasting information is incorporated, and as such the trends and probability models are available. This information with regards to the probability of having severe weather events can be included in current underwriting modules for every specified area market, country or even parcel.

Blockchain component and Smart Contract Function

Shilpa Pankaj: The staking concept is very interesting and although it is considered a regulatory hurdle at the moment, it could be an opportunity down the line.

Customize BEACON to less tech-ready markets

Shilpa Pankaj: Non-tech markets like the Asian market need an alternative proposal to mobile apps. BEACON should make available other platforms for such markets.

BEACON: ETHERISC is building on the application for features phones through text messages. The product can easily be deployed, as long as electronic payment systems are deployed in a country.

Make BEACON available to third world markets

Shilpa Pankaj: Consider the Asian market and in general third world countries market as a target market.

BEACON: BEACON can offer this ready solution to third world countries. Local expertise is nonetheless needed in weather forecasts and in obtaining historical data. The possibility of implementing BEACON in third world markets is mainly based on the local situation and readiness of these countries.

Cloud coverage in Drought Assessment

Shilpa Pankaj: Drought assessment in South Europe is based on cloud coverage which is not expected to create problems as cloud coverage is limited. Nonetheless, in areas where there is significant cloud coverage, alternative datasets should be considered.

BEACON: BEACON utilizes a combination of data i.e., remote sensing, optical, meteorological and sub data. Cloud coverage is indeed an issue. To this end, the MODIS component is being used which provides daily data and uses an 8day average of non-cloud data. On top of this temporal interpolation is applied in order to fill in the gaps of cloud covered images

Crop classification tool

Shilpa Pankaj: Consider a crop classification tool within BEACON, as it is a service that is needed by the Agl companies.

BEACON: A crop classification tool could potentially be added as a service. Such a user requirement has not been expressed up to now.

3.3 The AgI Enablers questionnaire

The questionnaire circulated to the AB (see annex) was relative to the BEACON business models and overall evaluation of the BEACON tool. Their feedback and evaluation of the BEACON tool are summarized in the following:

Ms Shilpa Pankaj

Guy Carpenter's is a reinsurance broker and as such the BEACON toolbox services are not directly relevant to us. Nonetheless, the service is of good use to our clients who are the Agriculture Insurance companies. While many of the services of the toolbox are being offered by various parametric & IT solution providers, they are very fragmented. BEACON project brings it all together from start till the end. All functionalities of the BEACON toolbox are most valuable from the client's perspective. RST, EO and smart contracting are considered to be the of most value.

BEACON could potentially fit in the BSBY (West Bangal) Tech-based Crop Insurance Scheme in India.

A functionality that could also be offered by the service is Soil Moisture Level using Wetness Index Data. It would be also interesting to see with reference to information on the comparison of actual vs Indexed loss data

The BEACON Toolbox will definitely be relevant for the Agriculture Insurance companies and is something Guy Carpenter's would consider buying. The Business Model best suited in our case is Tech-based claims management. It needs to be mentioned that there are similar services available in the market. ARBOL, Excess weather, Swiss re Parametric solutions, AXAClimate, Nephila Climate all have similar solutions. Nevertheless, not all of them use smart contracting. Additionally, there are about 100+ AgTech's companies providing servicing spanning across various platforms and modules like Geospatial Insights with WheaTrac, Planet Labs, Taranis, FarmersEdge, Sinergia, but as mentioned before their services are fragmented, unlike the BEACON toolbox.

This Toolbox comes timely to the market as many are looking for alternative tech driven claims management. We would definitely recommend the BEACON tool to our clients and some of Guy Carpenter's clients (Insurance companies) in the Asia Pacific could possibly like to adopt it. Notably, the markets of India, China, Philippines, Thailand & Vietnam are the ones of higher potential.

Mrs. Eleni Vakaki

The BEACON tool can play a complementary role to E-leaf, it being a data and index service provider. The crop profiling module, the yield estimations and the crop growth modelling could easily complement eLEAF services.

Looking at the crop monitoring and damage assessment calculation part, the tool could be more innovative in terms of technologies and data used to go a step further. Nonetheless, the combination of all the tools is what makes it most valuable in my opinion.

Overall, BEACON is a toolbox very useful for re/insurers

4. AgI Enablers Recommendations

A summary of recommendations / important aspects highlighted by the AgI Enablers throughout the project, are presented in the table below. Their comments are linked to specific mitigation actions that the BEACON project has to offer to the AgI sector. Relevant recommendations have been considered by the project partners in the realization of the project activities.

Name	Recommendations /Important aspects	BEACON Actions
Mrs. Eleni Vakaki	User needs identification across countries and in diverse environments. Will facilitate also the development of sustainable business models	<p>BEACON tried to engage as many relevant stakeholders as possible for all over the world through the Lighthouse Customers Group. Specifically, during this phase, questionnaires were circulated to all the LHC, established not only in EU but also in India and USA, collecting valuable feedback with regards to user needs.</p> <p>Furthermore, BEACON tries to include into its LHC Group, members not only for EU in order to explore and identify better the AgI sector's needs and requirements in diverse environments for further sustainability and viability.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP2; WP6</i></p>
Mrs. Eleni Vakaki Dr. Clement Atzberger Mr. Genillard Mr. Paul Meeusen	Validation of results in pilots as an ongoing procedure	<p>During the pilot implementation, all the provided services will be constantly validated and if it is needed, will be recalibrated in order to achieve the highest accuracy. The validation process will be done through the feedback from our pilot users with regards to the results provided to them via the BEACON toolbox. A more detailed validation plan will be developed in the following months.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP4; WP5</i></p>
Mrs. Eleni Vakaki Dr. Clement Atzberger	<p>1) Sustainable business models to address the needs of the markets</p> <p>2) Fitting business models to the diverse the needs of AgI companies</p>	<p>1) BEACON will identify 4 slightly different Business Models, that meet the needs and expectations of its core customer groups. The preliminary 4 models will also have a diverse mix of pricing models such as: Initial Subscription fee (depending on the ha insured) and a flat pricing policy of Premiums Insured, per year; or Flat pricing policy per ha of information processed, per year; with even "larger" packages" such as Yearly subscription plan (country based). Each of those models will be further "tuned" on the basis of operational validation with BEACON lighthouse customers,</p>

Name	Recommendations /Important aspects	BEACON Actions
		<p>aiming to achieve a high perceived value from our LHC while high willingness to pay for the BEACON services.</p> <p>2) To further support, the different actors' sizes and requirements in terms of services, BEACON allows the modular provision of its services coupled with a modular pricing.</p> <p>The latter is also supported by the "placement"/ provision of BEACON to our potential customers.</p> <p>Fitting business models to the diverse the needs of Agl companies.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP6</i></p>
Mr. Genillard; Dr. Clement Atzberger	Consideration to integrate BEACON toolbox in to the Agl's IT existing systems	<p>BEACON can be integrated into the existing IT systems either through the toolbox or by providing only the services. Offering these two options, each LHC will be able to decide whether the BEACON toolbox will be integrated into their systems or not.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP4</i></p>
Mrs. Eleni Vakaki Dr. Clement Atzberger Mr. Genillard Mr. Paul Meeusen	Trustworthy ground data for validation of services; Potential use of other data sources, e.g. drones	<p>From the early stages of the project, historical ground truth data have been collected from the LHC in order to process them and start the validation of the provided services. Moreover, more such data will be collected during the pilot implementation, for further calibration and validation of the services.</p> <p>BEACON has already taken into account and incorporated into its services other data sources, such as SAR (Sentinel-1), MODIS (8-day NDVI composites) and Sentinel-2 optical data. BEACON aspires as a further step to leverage on very high-resolution data (<10 m spatial resolution) through synergies with other providers.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP3</i></p>
Mr. Genillard	Largely communicate the benefits of EO, blockchain technologies to Agl service providers	<p>WP7 focuses at the broad and targeted communication and dissemination activities of the BEACON project. A dedicated Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan has been built and it is being implemented. It has set out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels that are being used, to effectively spread BEACON activities, achievements</p>

Name	Recommendations /Important aspects	BEACON Actions
		<p>and tangible results to targeted audiences, also becoming the cornerstone for the successful commercialization and market uptake of BEACON solutions.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP3</i></p>
<p>Dr. Ioannis Athanasiadis</p>	<p>Identify the potential BEACON customer profiles who would be interested in private insurance plans amongst your in-market partners and lighthouse partners.</p>	<p>BEACON is continuously engaging stakeholders from all over the world through the Lighthouse Customers Group. BEACON has included into its LHC Group, members not only for EU in order to explore and identify better the Agri sector's needs and requirements in diverse environments for further sustainability and viability. Additionally, through dissemination tools (i.e. website, social media) BEACON is running surveys / polls looking into the user – potential customer needs. Finally, BEACON is organizing events – workshops (e.g. AgriInsurance Meetup 2020) to encourage the engagement and expression of opinion of the Agri companies' needs.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP2; WP6, WP7</i></p>
<p>Ms. Shilpa Pankaj</p>	<p>A limiting factor when it comes to the agricultural sector, is that there is a different level of technological literacy at all levels to adopt this technology.</p>	<p>The BEACON tool was developed along with end users for the users so that it is useful and easy for them to understand, avoiding complex technological processes. To support, the different actors' sizes and requirements in terms of services, BEACON allows the modular provision of its services coupled with a modular pricing. Furthermore, it is available either as SAAS or DAAS, giving users the opportunity to assimilate it into their existing processes.</p> <p>The latter is also supported by the "placement"/ provision of BEACON to our potential customers. The "Go to the market strategy" also examines and evaluates the uptake of ICT by companies and presents integration solutions in different markets.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP2, WP4, WP6</i></p>
<p>Dr. Ioannis Athanasiadis</p>	<p>It is necessary to establish a collaboration between the Agri companies and EO experts in order to translate what we see from satellites into</p>	<p>BEACON emphasizes on collaborative development of services in order to produce services that are user friendly. In order to achieve this a co-creation process took place based in user needs and their active involvement. Furthermore, cooperation between Agri companies and EO experts has been established either through the consortium or the Agri Enablers, whilst in accordance to the established</p>

Name	Recommendations /Important aspects	BEACON Actions
	something useful for agricultural insurance.	<p>BEACON engagement strategy ensuring a dynamic interaction with the BEACON targeted audiences is of outmost importance (D7.1). Amongst the main target groups of the engagement strategy are Agl companies and the EO industry. Additionally, EO experts are considered as possibilities for the enhancement of the AB, to help us further simplify, where necessary, the information provided.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP2, WP4, WP7</i></p>
Mrs Eleni Vakaki	Insurance agents faced difficulties in promoting products due to restrictions in travelling which resulted in a decrease in sales volumes.	<p>The BEACON climatology service can provide the needed information to insurance agents so as to offer the “right” product to the potential client, even if physical presence or meeting would be impossible during COVID-19 situation.</p> <p>Enabling the insurance agents to provide the most appropriate product, in terms of costs and coverages, while having access to all related information would allow the insurance company to profitably serve the customers through an online channel.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP2, WP4, WP7</i></p>
	Farmers suffered losses in their income and are thus expected to be more reluctant to invest in insurance products. Insurance Prices need to be adjusted.	<p>The reduction of travelling and minimization of administrative costs can offer the Agl the ability to adjust their pricing policies. This can be tackled both by the implementation of the BEACON tool and the business models for sustainable growth and commercialization strategy of WP6.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP6</i></p>
	Index insurance is found to be more flexible and preferable for remoted areas.	<p>The overall aim of WP3 is to develop services based on earth observation products and atmospheric data. BEACON can serve either index/ parametric insurance scheme or calamity based one.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP3</i></p>
Mr Christopher Genillard	New social distancing rules are expected to accelerate digital loss	<p>The need to reduce the number of on-site visits for claim verification, in order to reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes has</p>

Name	Recommendations /Important aspects	BEACON Actions
	adjusting as in field estimates are difficult.	<p>become a necessity due to the pandemic. As Christopher is describing this should accelerate BEACON’s uptake as social contacts (farmer – insurer) due to pandemic have been minimised.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP 4 & 6</i></p>
	Farmers have suffered income loses in harvesting and processing and in some cases AgI companies supported farmers by allowing delayed payments of premiums.	<p>Given that farmers have suffered income loses AgI companies are in turn expected to be impacted. BEACON will reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes and contract handling, and design more accurate and personalized contracts thus supporting AgI companies through this crisis.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP 4, 5 & 6</i></p>
Mr. Paul Meeusen	Small and medium sized farmers have had to familiarize themselves with digital tools over the pandemic.	<p>The uptake of digital tools over the pandemic by a number of small and medium scale farmers is significant for the successful uptake of BEACON’s tool. This is a positive impact of the pandemic for the AgI sector, as it will allow AgI companies to use digital tools more widely. To support, the different actors’ sizes and requirements in terms of services, BEACON allows the modular provision of its services. The “Go to the market strategy” also examines and evaluates companies IST and presents integration solutions in different markets.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP6</i></p>
Ms. Shilpa Pankaj	Look into AgI markets of non-European countries i.e., the Asian market	<p>Over the co-creation process BEACON actively engaged 17 AgI actors (LHC), enabling the development of guidelines and requirements coming from the Agriculture Insurance sector at a global scale including Asian countries (i.e., Azerbaijan and India).</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP6</i></p>
Ms. Shilpa Pankaj	Adjust BEACON app to non-tech market needs	<p>The BEACON application can run on a feature phone through text messages as long as there is an electronic payment system in a country.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Relevant WPs: WP 4 & 5</i></p>

Name	Recommendations /Important aspects	BEACON Actions
Ms. Shilpa Pankaj	Factor in the BEACON model the impact of climate change on the pricing and underwriting.	<p>The climatology module is fed with historical data that dates back up to 50+ years for any type of field or indices. Additionally, weather forecasting information is incorporated, so the trends and probability models are available. This information can be included in current underwriting modules so that for every specified area market, country or even parcel with regards to the probability of having severe weather events.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP3, 4 & 5</i></p>
Mrs. Eleni Vakaki	Cloud coverage alternatives datasets should be considered for areas of high cloudiness	<p>BEACON utilizes a combination of data: remote sensing, optical, meteorological and sub data. Cloud coverage is indeed an issue. To this end, the MODIS component is being used which provides daily data and uses 8day averages of non-cloud data. On top of this temporal interpolation is applied in order to fill the gaps of cloud covered images.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP3, 4 & 5</i></p>
Mrs. Eleni Vakaki	Communicate risk alerts and monitor relative actions	<p>BEACON engine provides the insurance companies with early warnings of imminent extreme weather events and diseases outbreaks, as well as visualized confirmation of damage. Once the alert is deployed, they receive feedback on whether actions were taken by farmers.</p> <p><i>Relevant WPs: WP3. 4 &5</i></p>

Annex I Agl Enablers final questionnaire

Dear BEACON Agl Enablers,

As the BEACON project is coming to its end and based on its results, we kindly ask you to fill in the following questionnaire to provide us with your expert's feedback.

Please send us your replies by January 10, 2022.

1

How valuable is the BEACON toolbox services to your business?

High Please give a short justification:

Medium

Low

1

How innovative do you think the service is?

High Please give a short justification:

Medium

Low

1

Which functionality of the BEACON Toolbox do you consider to be the most valuable for your operations?

1

Do you miss some information/functionality that could be offered by the service?

1

Would you consider buying the BEACON Toolbox and to implement it in your company?

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Which BEACON Business Model would suit you best?#

Do you know of any similar services in the market? If yes, please list them.#

Would you recommend the BEACON Toolbox to your colleagues and to whom (company profile: big or small / country -- market / etc.)?#

Thank You!

Project Partners:#

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